

Naturally occurring odd number fatty acids in the rhizome oil of *Alpinia speciosa* K. Schum.

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Abstract : Contrary to usual observations, the rhizome oil of *Alpinia speciosa* K. Schum. is found to contain not only one but as much as five odd number carbon atoms containing natural fatty acids, apart from eight even carbon fatty acids. Among the fatty acids containing odd number of carbon atoms, the useful pentadecanoic acid (C-15) is main (21.9%) and others are C-23 (5.7%), C-13 (1.9%), C-11 (3.1%) and C-9 (0.1%). Among the fatty acids containing even number of carbon atoms, the highly unsaturated linolenic acid (C-18:3) is main (27.4%) and the next is the very useful arachidic acid (C-20), 22.4%. The total saturated fatty acids constitute 65.7% and unsaturated 34.3%.

Keywords : *Alpinia speciosa*, *Alpinia zerumbet*, *Alpinia nutans*, Zingiberaceae, fatty oil, natural fatty acids.

Introduction

Alpinia speciosa K. Schum. (syn. *Alpinia zerumbet* Burt. and R.M. Smith, *Alpinia nutans* Rosc., *Catimbium speciosum* Holtt., *Languas speciosa* Small., *Zerumbet speciosum* Wendl. and *Costus zerumbet* Pers.¹), called *Chatian* in Hindi, belongs to Zingiberaceae family. A handsome, rhizomatous, perennial herb, upto 3 m in height, occurring in the Eastern Himalayas from West Bengal eastwards, and frequently cultivated in gardens for its foliage and showy flowers, *A. speciosa* is also planted in hedges². The flowers are beautiful and the whole plant fragrant like the cardamom. The rhizome of the plant is useful in rheumatism and catarrhal affections³. In affections of the gastrointestinal tract, the drug can be used like other volatile oils³. The rhizome exhibits anti-ulcer and antiplatelet activity⁴ as well. In China, it is used as a carminative, astringent, tonic and sedative⁵. The rhizome contains 5,6-dehydrokawain and dihydro 5,6-dehydrokawain that have been reported to inhibit the aggregation of ATP release from rabbit platelets induced by arachidonic acid and collagen⁶. Very recently, the presence of phenolic compounds in rhizomes has been reported by Elzaawely *et al.* in a Japanese sample and their use in meat, dairy and bakery has been suggested⁷.

No systematic work has so far been reported on fatty oil from the rhizome of *A. speciosa*. Phytochemical screen-

ing of rhizome oil is a subject of intensive research to explore new alternative source for conventional oils. In the present work it was, therefore, considered of interest to isolate and identify the fatty acids present in the rhizome. It is the first report of this kind. Quantitative separation of the natural esters is difficult and often impossible even with the most refined technique. It is, therefore, common practice to convert natural fats and waxes to a single type of simple monoester, usually the methyl ester or the free acid, prior to any attempt of separation. This technique has been used in the present work.

Results and discussion

Oil obtained by extraction through petroleum ether (60–80 °C) is a reddish brown viscous oil with mild spicy odour (yield 2.01% w/w, d^{30} 0.822 g mL⁻¹; $[\alpha]_D^{30} +2.08'$; n^{30} 1.38; acid value 34.7; saponification value 183.7; iodine value 69.2; clearly soluble in petroleum ether, diethyl ether, benzene and chloroform). A high acid value points out towards the presence of enough free fatty acids in it. However, separation of unsaponifiable matter, if any, is necessary before the fatty acid analysis. In fact, all natural fats contain some unsaponifiable matter that may consist of hydrocarbons, long-chain aliphatic alcohols, sterols etc. In natural fats, this unsaponifiable matter usually represents a minor fraction (0.5 to 2%)⁸, but in the case of *Alpinia speciosa* rhizomes the present

study has indicated it to be higher (23.7%) in quantity (Table 1). If unsaponifiable matter is not removed, it will appear subsequently at some step in the separation of the fatty acids or esters⁹. Thus, such a separation has been carried out and GLC analysis of the remaining (saponifiable matter) and has then lead us to the identification of constituents representing 99.97% of the oil.

Table 1. Broad composition of rhizome oil of *Alpinia speciosa* K. Schum.

Unsaponifiable matter	23.7%
Fatty matter	58.9%
Saturated fatty acids	65.7%
Unsaturated fatty acids	34.3%

Interestingly the results have indicated the *A. speciosa* rhizome oil to be containing a wide range of, C₉ to C₂₄, among which five are the fatty acids containing odd number of carbon atoms. The results support the fact that not only the fatty acids containing even number of carbon atoms but many fatty acids containing odd number carbon atoms also occur naturally. Presence of C₉ (0.1%), C₁₁ (3.1%), C₁₃ (1.9%), C₁₅ (21.9%) and C₂₃ (5.7%) are indicated in this oil (Table 2), besides the usual even carbon fatty acids. All the detected odd carbon fatty acids are saturated.

Table 2. Fatty acid composition of rhizome oil of *Alpinia speciosa* K. Schum.

Fatty acid	Retention time (min)	Percentage
C-9:0	5.7	0.1
C-11:0	8.1	3.1
C-12:0	11.0	1.6
C-13:0	12.5	1.9
C-14:0	16.8	1.0
C-15:0	18.9	21.9
C-18:0	20.8	2.4
C-18:1	23.0	6.9
C-18:3	24.7	27.4
C-20:0	27.0	22.4
C-22:0	30.8	2.1
C-23:0	32.8	5.7
C-24:0	35.3	3.5

Saturated fatty acids (even and odd) constitute 65.7%; arachidic acid, C-20:0 (22.4%) and pentadecanoic acid, C-15:0 (21.9%) being the main. Arachidic acid is used as a lubricant and emulsifier in industrial preparations¹⁰. It

is also used as a surfactant, softner, dispersing agent and in detergents¹¹. On the other hand, the odd number carbon containing pentadecanoic acid is a floral compound. Its occurrence in rhizome oil is rare. Species utilise this acid in its chemical communication system¹². It can also be used as a marker for intake of milk fat¹³. Next among the saturated fatty acids are tricosanoic acid, C-23:0 (5.7%), lignoceric acid, C-24:0 (3.5%) and undecanoic acid, C-11:0 (3.1%). Tricosanoic acid is simply a chromatographic standard but lignoceric acid is an ant repellent¹⁴. Undecanoic acid is used to prepare ointments with dermatophilic activity¹⁵. Other saturated acids detected are stearic, C-18:0 (2.4%), behenic, C-22:0 (2.1%), lauric, C-12:0 (1.6%), myristic, C-14:0 (1.0%) and nonanoic acid, C-9:0 (0.1%).

Unsaturated fatty acids constitute 34.3%; linolenic acid, C-18:3 (27.4%) being the main. Linolenic acid is a popular dietary source for health and nutrition and its intake reduces risk of coronary heart disease¹⁶. Oleic acid C-18:1, is also present in sufficient quantity (6.9%). Apart from being a soap base, oleic acid is used in surface coatings and ore floatation¹⁷.

Experimental

Authentic rhizomes of *A. speciosa* were procured from Dehradun and authenticity verified by Forest Research Institute, Dehradun. A specimen has been deposited in the herbarium of Plant Medicine Section of the Chemistry Department of Gurukula Kangri University, Haridwar, under the registry no. 17/15 and available for inspection. The rhizomes were washed with lukewarm water and dried in shed. Extraction in petroleum ether (60–80 °C) was carried out by usual procedures using a Soxhlet to obtain the oily material.

Determination of unsaponifiable matter : The oil (5 g) obtained by extraction through petroleum ether was saponified by refluxing with 50 mL of N/2 alc. KOH for about 2 h. The alcohol was distilled off completely. The soap so formed was diluted with 500 mL water and the unsaponifiable matter extracted with three 100 mL portions of petroleum ether in a separating funnel. The ethereal extract was washed several times with water and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. Removal of the solvent under vacuum yielded the unsaponifiable matter, 1.184 g. The soap solution was collected separately.

Determination of total fatty matter : The aqueous soap solution obtained above was acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid and warmed on a water bath to regenerate

the mixed fatty acids. The solution was cooled and liberated acids were extracted with ether. The ethereal extract was washed few times with water and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. On removal of the solvent from the dried ethereal extract, a mixture of mixed fatty acids (2.947 g) was obtained.

Preparation of methyl esters : Methyl esters of the fatty acids were prepared by esterifying the mixture with methanol in 1% sulphuric acid on a water bath for 4 h¹⁸. Mixture was cooled and extracted with ether. The ethereal extract was washed first with 5% K₂CO₃ (3 times) and then with water and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. On removal of solvent, the mixture of methyl esters was obtained.

Fatty acid analysis : The analysis of fatty acid methyl esters was carried out on Chemito Gas Liquid Chromatograph fitted with FID (260 °C). The temperature of the injector was maintained at 250 °C. Stainless steel Silar 15% column (length 9 feet) was used with nitrogen as carrier gas (40 mL/min). Split was maintained at 60 mL/min and purge was maintained at 2 mL/min. The oven temperature was programmed from 150–230 °C (with increase in temperature 3 °C/min) followed by a final hold up time of 25 min. Methyl esters were identified by comparing the retention times of standard fatty acid methyl esters and also by their coinjection, wherever needed.

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